
USING ELEMENTS OF DIFFERENTIATED LEARNING IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract.

The essence of differentiated education and upbringing is to provide psychological and methodological assistance to students in their achievement of success in educational and cognitive activities. The article deals with innovative pedagogical approaches in teaching foreign languages: differentiated learning.

Keywords.

differentiated learning, methods and ways, language material, educational tasks

Introduction.

Every year, more and more changes are taking place in the education system of our country Uzbekistan, causing an increase in the amount of information and complication of the requirements for its perception within the framework of the academic discipline. Therefore, the quality of the educational process largely depends not only on the amount of information received, but also on the learning technology aimed at its assimilation and further application.

Main part:

Today, the curriculum organized by the teacher in the classroom system is focused on the entire class, which means that it affects the effectiveness of the knowledge gained in different ways, determining the level of development of students. This problem plays an important role in teaching foreign languages, especially English, since the disciplines of the language being studied are among the most difficult and cause certain difficulties for many students. So, for example, students with developed logical thinking are able to better and faster learn educational material in English lessons, in contrast to those who have developed figurative thinking [3,174]. Thus, it is impossible to achieve the assimilation of language material by the entire group of students at the same high level. The emergence of students' interest in teaching English largely depends on how the

teacher develops the curriculum. It is the technology of differentiated learning, used within the discipline "foreign language", that can play a significant role in improving the quality of the educational process in the field of language teaching.

An important task facing an English teacher is to organize comfortable learning conditions, taking into account the individual characteristics of each student, which will improve the quality of foreign language training of students. Accompanying the lesson with various forms, methods and ways of presenting language material, the teacher increases the interest of students in the development and practical application of learning tasks. The use of elements of differentiated learning in English lessons activates the desire of students for knowledge; students feel responsible, get used to self-organization. The main task of the teacher at the same time is to arouse the interest of students in the subject, to arouse the desire to further study a foreign language. Thus, we see that the study of the theoretical and methodological aspects of the construction of English lessons that implement the idea of differentiated learning is an important area of scientific and pedagogical research. Let's consider the definition of the concept of "differentiated learning". In Latin, differentiation means division. Differentiation of education is considered as a way of organizing the educational process, focused on the individual abilities of each student.

The purpose of differentiated learning is to create comfortable conditions for the educational process based on the abilities and interests of students in order to achieve maximum results in learning activities. It is necessary to take into account the fact that in each topic of the lesson the necessary lower level of knowledge and skills is determined, on the basis of which an increased level of assimilation of the material is formed. To achieve the desired result of educational activity, it is necessary to take into account the individual typological characteristics of the student (for example, the state of the student's nervous system indicates the speed of his perception of information and its subsequent processing). The implementation of this learning technology can help not only to develop the qualities of the student's personality, but also to master the minimum knowledge necessary for his further education [6,130]. Thus, identifying the characteristic features of students is an important task for a teacher who implements differentiated learning in the educational process. One of the ways to determine the individual characteristics of students is to conduct computer testing among students in a class based on the use of a specially designed set of questions. A.N. Leontiev defines differentiated learning from three positions, to which he refers the

psychological-pedagogical, social and didactic approaches [20, 93]. According to the psychological and pedagogical approach, differentiated learning is seen as the individualization of learning, based on the creation of optimal conditions for identifying the inclinations, developing the interests and abilities of each student. The social approach involves a targeted impact on the formation of the individual creative, professional potential of society in order to use rationally the capabilities of each member in society in its relationship with society.

The didactic approach involves solving the actual problems of technical universities by creating a new methodological system for differentiated teaching of students, based on a fundamentally new motivational basis. A means of differentiated learning is the division by the teacher in the process of teaching the class into levels, taking into account the characteristics that define each student. These characteristics include memory, attention, imagination, thinking, the ability of each student [11,240].

The technology of differentiated learning can be used not only when dividing students into small groups, taking into account their individual characteristics and abilities in the classroom, but also when dividing classes into different profiles and areas on the territory of technical universities, due to which differentiated learning develops. in two forms: internal and external. Each (of the indicated) form of a differentiated approach has its own description. A characteristic feature of intra-class level differentiation is the student's ability to choose the level of study of the discipline that he considers sufficient in accordance with his mental abilities and interests. Differentiation of the external level includes the organization of separate specialized classes, technical institutes for the purpose of in-depth study of individual subjects in accordance with the interests of students. The use of these forms of differentiated learning at one of the presented levels allows teachers to unlock the potential of each student.

Based on this approach, two main forms of organizing educational activities in English lessons are distinguished:

1. Differentiation according to the ways of organizing the collective educational activities of students (group, individual, joint work of the teacher with students).
2. Differentiation of the content of educational tasks (according to the level of complexity and the degree of necessity for learning and further development of students).

Group activity provides for the division of the class into groups according to the level of intellectual development of students. The content of the tasks for each group should be developed in accordance with the skills and abilities of the students. The method of organizing educational activities, focused on the individual work of each student, assumes that the teacher distributes tasks to each student, different in level of complexity, depending on the identified characteristics of the students [14,133]. The joint activity of the teacher with the students assumes that the educational process proceeds under the guidance of the teacher. However, this way of organizing learning activities assumes that the teacher provides assistance in the process of solving problems to those students who experience certain difficulties; the rest of the students work independently.

The process of teaching English involves the organization of level differentiation of work in the lesson at all its stages: when studying new material, as well as when consolidating and repeating what has already been passed. The teacher must ensure a continuous flow of new information to the best of his abilities and the abilities of his students.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, we can say that our study does not reveal all the issues related to differentiated learning and its use in the disciplines of foreign language education, but represents a certain attempt to systematize and structure the knowledge available in this area and can become the basis for further research.

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